

Interaction of motor-transmission-inverter of an electric axle unit

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Abstract. In this paper, the changes in the e-mobility market towards the increasing demand for integrated e-axles with a specific set of requirements will be explained. The introduction of the WLTP will be included in the specific efficiency requirements for e-axles. Valeo Siemens eAutomotive as a global supplier for high voltage e-axle and electric drivetrain components faces the new demands by an integrated scalable e-axle platform. On the basis of an analysis of performance, efficiency and NVH requirements, it is shown, how an holistic optimization of an e-axle could fulfil performance, efficiency, NVH, weight and cost expectations at the same time. Focusing on efficiency and NVH, influence factors on system and component level are deeply discussed. For the component e-motor, a detailed analysis concerning influence and improvement measures for efficiency and NVH is presented. Finally, an e-motor design workflow including CAE based optimization to realize e-motors fostering powerful, efficient and quiet e-axles is explained.

Keywords: e-axle, e-motor design, efficient drivetrain

1 Introduction

1.1 Market demands for electric drivetrains

Within the past 5 years, e-mobility lived a strong growth with accelerating market and product penetration. Driven by legislative boundaries like CO₂ limitations in the EU, USA and China and driving prohibitions in certain areas for combustion engine cars, many new hybrid electric (HEV) and electric cars (EV) as well as car platforms have been presented by nearly all OEMs. Besides the legal restrictions, strong improvements concerning the high voltage batteries lead to an increasing interest of the end customers in electric cars. The energy resp. power density of today's batteries has been strongly increased over the last years, while the price per kWh drastically dropped. These conditions enabled larger and more powerful car batteries realizing driving ranges of more than 300 km or even above 400 km.

Based on this changing situation on the market, also the demand for electric drivetrain components and entire electric drivetrains has changed. Focusing on battery electric vehicles, the electric drivetrain consists of an e-axle unit. In analogy to combustion engine cars, there are one or two driven axles. Such an axle contains an electric

motor, an inverter and a transmission including a differential. Using only one motor and inverter to drive the two wheels of one axle is the common drivetrain architecture today.

To provide first (H)EVs to the market, existing car platforms have been equipped with electric drivetrain components in the past. Compactness and fitting into the available space were major criteria. As high driving ranges were not possible due to missing battery capacity, the focus was set on power resp. torque density to create a positive customer experience in terms of acceleration and agility. There were nearly no e-axle solutions available on the market which was the reason, that motor, inverter and transmission have been combined from several suppliers and have been developed according to a component specification independently of each other. Peak and continuous torque resp. power were the key performance indicators. Efficiency over a driving cycle at NEDC times and NVH have not been of highest relevance.

With the described market changes, also the demand for electric drivetrains fully changed. Instead of components, e-axle drives are considered. Performance and installation space tended to a self-clustering in:

Table 1. Typical power classes of e-axles

Power	Utilization
< 100 kW	Mostly supporting axle (hybrid or 4WD)
100 kW – 200 kW	Main class for EVs
200 kW – 300 kW	Premium class EVs
> 300 kW	Premium sport EVs

Besides these performance boundaries, strong focus is set on efficiency over the recently released WLTP driving cycle as battery driving range is and becomes an important selling point. Furthermore, from the customer expectation of an entirely quiet EV, the acoustic behavior (NVH) of the e-axle became an important requirement.

Valeo Siemens eAutomotive as a global supplier for high voltage e-axles and electric drivetrain components has developed a scalable platform of integrated e-axles to deliver appropriate solutions to OEMs.

1.2 E-axle arrangements

According to the drivetrain demands for today's and future electric car platforms, common e-axle system topologies became accepted in the market for typical passenger car applications. Fig. 1 presents the key components of an e-axle.

Fig. 1. Components of an e-axle.

System integration means in this context, the mechanical arrangement of the three main components in a way, that the functional parts of every component are separate but all non-functional parts like housings, interconnections, bearing shields are reduced to a minimum and commonly used wherever possible:

- Motor and transmission sharing one bearing shield
- Inverter attached on the motor-transmission housing
- Inverter-motor-connection via internal busbars
- Single speed transmission incl. differential and optional park lock
- Common external cooling supply, cooling inverter, motors and transmission
- Only HV DC connection and LV communication connection to the car

These measures increase the compactness of an e-axle and reduce material cost compared to three dedicated separate components.

2 Interaction of the components in an e-axle

Following the explanation in the introduction, early electric drivetrains have just been the sum of the different components. In this chapter, it will be explained why it is not sufficient to specify and design the components independently from each other and how an e-axle can become more than just the sum of the components.

Focus in this analysis and synthesis will be set on performance, efficiency and NVH.

2.1 General efficiency analysis

The component and drivetrain efficiency is a key aspect. Not only leading to a car USP in terms of driving autonomy resp. WLTP driving range. In addition, size and performance of the e-axle are strongly affected. Higher efficiency is equal to lower losses, which reduces the cooling effort and/or the components temperature. By typically limited means of cooling, the thermally possible output torque resp. power increases for more efficient systems.

Fig. 2. Typical vehicle torque speed curves for 150 kW power class including exemplary WLTP operating points.

In Fig. 2, exemplary e-axis torque speed curves for peak operation and continuous operation are shown for a 150 kW class. Considering the exemplary WLTP operation points, it is evident that all points are below continuous power limits and thus below 50% of maximum torque.

As the WLTP provides a basis for official car range definition, the whole e-axis need to be optimized for low load efficiency. Therefore, the power flow and different types of losses and their influence factors shall be investigated, Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Power flow in e-axis including different loss quantities.

Evaluating the power flow from Fig. 3, it is obvious, that additional losses at the wheel side have to be transferred from the battery through the entire drivetrain, creating additional losses in all components.

Considering the different loss types that occur in electric drivetrains, it can be derived, that increasing speed and frequency ends up in a decrease of efficiency. Higher electrical frequencies mostly need higher switching frequencies, which evoke higher switching losses P_{SW} in the inverter. The conduction losses P_{CD} are only affected by the current amplitude. In the electric motor, higher frequencies lead to higher additional

winding loss P_{WD} which can be compensated by more costly winding designs with negative influence on the power density. Furthermore, the magnetic loss in the stator and rotor core of the motor increase with the electric frequency, which can only be partly compensated by using electrical steel of higher quality or reduced thickness at higher cost.

The specific loss per kg in the rotor and stator iron parts a given by:

$$p_{Fe} = k_h \cdot f \cdot \hat{B}^2 + k_c \cdot f^2 \cdot \hat{B}^2 + k_e \cdot f^{1.5} \cdot \hat{B}^{1.5} \quad (1)$$

Besides the constants k_h for hysteresis loss, k_c for eddy current loss and k_e for excess loss, the loss density depends on the electric frequency f and the magnet flux density B . For a high utilization of the motor, the induction B is driven close to the saturation of the electric sheet. The frequency f is linear to the speed. Core losses not only result from the fundamental frequency but in a significant amount also from harmonics. Increasing utilization and / or increasing speed foster augmented core loss due to a raised harmonic content in the magnetic flux.

On mechanical side, higher speed result in higher friction losses in bearing P_{BR} , in rotating parts in air or oil P_{FR} and in contact between the teeth of the gears P_{GR} .

Cooling aspects may not be neglected in this context. In terms of peak power, motors can be downsized by increasing speed. Considering continuous power, the capabilities of the cooling system have to be respected. Assuming same peak power and same efficiency, a small high speed motor generates the same loss heat as a large low speed motor but with a higher loss density resp. less volume / surface. Thus, a more efficient motor cooling is needed.

Hence, considering the entire drivetrain system, the transmission ratio has to be chosen taking the influence on each single component into account.

2.2 Efficiency influence

The following example serves to demonstrate the cross influences between the e-axle components.

Two different motors with identical torque resp. power speed curves are compared. The efficiency over the operation range differs slightly in favor for motor A at high load and low speed. Motor B is right opposing in favor for high speed and lower torque.

Fig. 4. Efficiency comparison for two slightly different motors: motor A (left), motor B (middle), difference in efficiency (right).

For high and peak load operations, motor A is clearly superior. For cycle operation in low and medium load with medium speed, motor B shows clear advantages. A purely motor based choice would lead to motor A.

Adding the consideration of the inverter, the current demand of the motors becomes important.

Fig. 5. Current demand: motor A (left), motor B (middle), difference in current (right)

Due to the higher current demand of motor B, the losses in the inverter increase which leads to a reduced efficiency. In a combined consideration over WLTP operation, the system with motor A results in a better efficiency than the one with motor B.

This example shows, that neither a single component consideration is sufficient nor the focus on specific working points.

2.3 NVH influence

The awareness for the topic NVH (noise vibration and harshness) has strongly increased within the last years. Pure electric cars are promoted to be completely quiet especially in low speed operation. This resulted in a low threshold for acceptable noise. Noise in a car can generally be created or emitted by any component of the vehicle. For the e-axle, it can be reduced to two requirements.

1. The e-axle may not emit noise above an acceptable limit (airborne noise)
2. The e-axle may not induce vibrations into the car exciting other components to emit unacceptable noise (structural borne noise)

Furthermore, a differentiation into excitation and response is useful. The mechanisms of vibration and noise excitation are different for every component and will be treated more in detail for the e-motor in the corresponding section. The analysis of the structural response behavior is a topic on e-axle level as such a behavior strongly depends on the mounting position and conditions. A consideration on component level is only possible in a limited way.

Fig. 6 shows the different contributors to the overall NVH behavior of an e-axle. Requirements resp. limits can be given in different ways as vibration limits, noise limits, specified for bench tests or for in car operation.

Fig. 6. NVH related influence factors and dependencies in e-axes.

2.4 System design

A first step in the system design typically is the definition of the general e-axle topology – offset or transaxle. In most application cases, the given installation space only allows one of the two solutions. For a general platform approach, an offset design offers higher flexibility concerning adaptations for specific applications.

For the definition of the transmission ratio, different aspects have to be taken into account:

- Max. vehicle speed → max. motor speed → max. inverter frequency
- Torque demand → motor diameter → inverter current
- Power at high speed → motor iron losses → thermal capabilities
- Lubrication → fluid losses → general thermal management

The limiting factors for the different performance key points are presented in Fig. 7.

Fig. 7. Performance requirements and limiting factors.

Based on an existing product portfolio of e-motors and inverters, basic e-axes variants are virtually generated and compared concerning the relevant requirements. The most promising setup is taken into more detailed evaluation where the parameters are identified, which will be optimized for each component.

Fig. 8. E-axle design workflow.

Input for the motor optimization could be e.g.:

- High partial load efficiency with minimum current need
- Low vibration in certain frequency range
- Torque ripple below a certain value to avoid torsional oscillation in the entire drivetrain
- Interface accuracy to avoid transmission NVH issues

3 Motor

3.1 Design approach for high performance e-motor

In the proceeding sections, it was presented, which important boundary conditions have to be respected to design a motor leading to an optimized overall e-axle. In terms of e-motors, the joint venture Valeo Siemens eAutomotive can rely on more than 130 years of experience in e-motor design and production of Siemens and consequently transfers the today's requirements in powerful and efficient e-motors.

The steps from the first definitions till to an initial design are presented in Fig. 9.

Fig. 9. Motor design approach

To be able to realize new e-motors in an efficient way, the design is based on Valeo Siemens' existing and constantly improving motor platform. The general topology of a new e-motor is combined out of existing building blocks where parameters are adjusted or new variants developed to the specific needs.

3.2 Performance and efficiency consideration

In a first step, the given performance requirements have to be met. This must be fulfilled with the initial design. Evaluating the detailed simulation results and reference measurements, to characterize the behavior of the motor.

Fig. 10. Analysis of losses in e-motor.

In terms of efficiency, the different loss components in the relevant working points are analyzed in detail (see Fig. 10). By understanding the root causes, appropriate measures are defined to reduce the e-motor losses.

A first set of measures is related to materials, e.g. reducing high frequency iron losses by thinner electric steel sheet. On the other hand, changing the winding composition to reduce AC winding losses.

A second set of measures is related to design, e.g. changing the rotor topology to reduce several harmonics in the air gap field. Design adjustment measures will be considered in context of a design optimization.

A third set of measures is related to motor operation by the inverter. E.g. additional AC winding losses due to inverter switching. These points typically are addressed on system level.

3.3 NVH consideration

Motor NVH consists of different categories. It can be separated in excitation related and transfer path related. Concerning the transfer path and resonance behavior, the e-motor is comparable to any other mechanical system where all means of stiffening, increase of damping etc. can be applied. Therefore, the focus in this section will be set on the excitation side. The different contributors to NVH related excitation forces are listed in Fig. 11.

Fig. 11. Different types of NVH excitations in e-motors.

When analyzing the occurring orders (e.g. in bench tests), there can be differentiated between two categories:

1. The so-called regular electromagnetic order, which are present due to the design even in a perfectly built motor and fully visible in simulation.
2. The irregular orders, which cannot be explained based on a perfect CAD or CAE model. They are related to deviations in parts, production process or operating conditions and thus much more complicated to capture.

For integral slot windings, the regular orders are multiples of the number of poles, including the number of slots. Their low order mode shapes are limited to mode 0 (pumping mode) and multiples of the number of poles. Critical for round structures like e-motors are especially mode 1 (one-directional radial pull) and mode 2 (ovalization mode) as they show significant sensitivities for rotor and stator. Mode 0 is relevant as well. For higher modes, the sensitivity strongly decreases making them only critical combined with a high excitation level.

The amplitudes of the different components (radial, tangential, axial) are calculated via the magnetic field components in the air gap in CAE simulations, using a 2-D-FFT-

analysis to separate into time harmonic orders and spacial modes. Fig. 12 shows exemplary 2-D-force-plots for a typical 8-pole e-motor with 48 slots. Only mode types and harmonic orders 0, 8, 16, ... occur.

Fig. 12. Magnetic tooth forces in the air gap of an 8-pole e-motor with 48 slots

To evaluate the influence of the different mode-order-combinations, the forces are transferred into structural dynamic CAE simulations where the system response is calculated. For a given slot-pole-configuration, the regular orders cannot be fully eliminated, but their amplitudes / level can be significantly reduced by design optimizations. Therefore, critical sets are taken as target values into the design optimization.

All orders found in tests, which are not shown in Fig. 12 are considered as irregular orders. They only occur due to deviation from ideal design and operating conditions. Among them are typically deformation modes 1 and 2, harmonic orders equal to the number of pole $2p \pm 1, \pm 2$ etc. An overview of root causes for irregular orders is given in Fig. 13. If these orders occur, the root cause is analyzed in detail considering the specific conditions like parts quality and dimensions, operation conditions, control settings etc. E.g., limits in terms of typical tolerances and production process are used for sensitivity studies in the electromagnetic and structural dynamic CAE models to evaluate their influence and the design robustness.

Fig. 13. Causes for irregular NVH excitations orders in e-motors.

Valeo Siemens eAutomotive developed over the last years a database with possible mode-order-combinations, their typical root cause including all known process, control and material influences and appropriate countermeasures to foster a prompt solution of NVH issues.

3.4 Optimization

Optimization in e-motor design reaches from the manual comparison of only 2 variants up to fully automated multi-criteria multi-domain optimization. In this context, we are following a semi-automated optimization, which considers different physical domains without a fully coupled multi-domain tool landscape.

Focusing on efficiency and NVH excitation improvement targets for an existing basic design while maintaining performance and dimensional boundary conditions, the main CAE simulation is in the electromagnetic domain.

Respecting practical usability and reasonable simulation time, several limitations are given based on engineering judgement resp. experience as well as production knowledge, which significantly decreases the numerical optimization complexity.

The general proceeding is depicted in Fig. 14.

Fig. 14. Motor optimization workflow.

The optimization workflow is exemplarily demonstrated for an efficiency and NVH optimization, Fig. 15. The first large scale run returns several hundred possible variants. Focusing on those close to the Pareto front and adding further limiting conditions downscaled the plurality of variants to less than 100.

Fig. 15. Optimization of efficiency and NVH.

By evaluating influences on the inverter and the manufacturing process, the number of favorable designs is reduced to less than 10. For these most promising variants, detailed analysis in all domains are performed to evaluate even slight differences. Based on these results and on engineering judgement, the final design is chosen.

An overview of promising variations is given in Table 2, listing typical variation parameters and the tradeoff, which has to be made when tuning resp. optimizing these values. In general, measures for cycle efficiency and NVH are mostly coincident but fully conflictive to maximum torque and continuous torque resp. power requirements. Thermal motor performance and influence on the inverter current have to be evaluated in detail. Hence, for the fine-tuning, all disciplines need to be taken into account and being involved in the overall optimization loop.

Table 2. Example of tradeoff for typical parameter variations

Parameter	1 st dependency	2 nd dependency
Air gap size:	Torque per magnet/ampere ⇔	Harmonic filtering (NVH, loss)
Number of turns:	Minimal inv. current ⇔	Power at high speed
Rotor topology:	Torque per magnet/ampere ⇔	Harmonic content in field, ripple
Length scaling:	Torque per magnet/ampere ⇔	Active mass, iron loss

By means of CAE based optimization, comprehensive improvements especially related to NVH and efficiency could be achieved. On NVH side, a reduction of critical orders by more than 50% was validated by measurements and cycle efficiency improvements of more than 1% just on motor level with a baseline already above 90% were reached.

4 Conclusion

In this paper, the changed requirements towards electric drivetrains in the today's and future automotive market have been explained and the need for integrated e-axle units was derived. It has been shown, how only holistically optimized e-axles could fulfil performance, efficiency, NVH, weight and cost expectations at the same time. For the component e-motor, a detailed analysis of the influence factors concerning efficiency and NVH as well as their optimization has been presented. Valeo Siemens eAutomotive implemented this proceeding and the improvement measures in their design process to deliver integrated scalable e-axle solutions best fitting to customer needs.